

The Role of the Jordanian Embroidery in Preserving the Non-verbal language of the Cultural Heritage

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 19, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 19, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Embroidery, Non-verbal language, Costumes, Cultural Heritage</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4550917</p>	<p><i>The art of embroidery is considered one of the ancient folk arts of dazzling beauty and masterfully depending on the needle and thread and a high artistic taste to draw artistic paintings with bright and beautiful threads embroidered on clothes and fabrics as aesthetic paintings in multiple forms, carrying with them the legacy of the past and its originality. Traditionally three types of clothes for women exist in Jordan. Westernized females in new western clothing. Quite devout women wear Libisshar'i or jilbab. It is a buttons front's dress by a scarfed neck, which is a full body length dress with long sleeves. Religious women's shops in Jordan are popular. Several other nations Female shops Shar'i from Jordan. The national costume is indeed the third form of dress. This is a woven garment, in which the designs of the area of which the wearer comes are embroidered and sewn.</i></p> <p><i>The purpose of this study is to show the role of the Jordanian Embroidery in Preserving the Non-verbal language of the Cultural Heritage, the researcher used samples of traditional costumes from different cities in Jordan such as Ajloun, Salt, Irbid, Jarash, Maan, and the beduin folklore. The researcher collected photos representing different styles accompanied with historical background about each.</i></p> <p><i>Finally, the researcher made some interviews with some people who are interested in folklore and its role in preserving cultural identity.</i></p>

Introduction

Jordanian folk costumes are part of the culture and identity of the people of Jordan, and the costumes, especially women, are distinguished by their diversity due to the diversity of the geography in Jordan, with some commonalities between the various costumes, some of which are handcrafted and decorated to suit the environment.

The Jordanian dress has social, religious, economic and geographic connotations. Each region has its own decorations. Affluent families used gold and silver threads and other threads, fabrics and expensive materials for embroidery, while poor families used cotton and wool threads to decorate and embroider their garments.

The colors of the Jordanian traditional dress also indicate the age of the woman. The red band is worn by the young woman and the black band is worn by the elderly woman. A young married woman also wears a dress decorated in different colors from the dress of single women, each according to his region.

Each occasion has a dress and its own decorations such as work dresses, joy and sadness, and wedding dresses have a special status and certain specifications, so you find the colored dresses decorated with golden threads, and you find the white dress and its brightly embroidered decorations as an expression of love and loyalty.

Jordanian women's dress expresses its social and cultural functions and reflects the local environment in its social and cultural frameworks and in the determinants of natural formation in terms of climate and terrain, in addition to what it expresses in terms of a person's social position and his position in the social ladder of any society. Therefore, traditional dress of Jordanian women is distinguished by its abundance and diversity.

For starters, in North Jordan ladies wear multicolored three-angle cotton coats of black cotton. Throughout Central Jordan, ladies wear silk clothes made of seventeen yards (seventeen meters), with ten-foot (3 meter) in size sleeves. The buttons, as well as the hem of the cap, are stitched in blue. A plain cross-stitch, but as a foundation for intricate modelling and repeating natural (i.e. plumage, plants, trees or tides) and abstract motives (zig zag pattern or triangles), is being utilized as the primary form of border. These are the clothes that are carved with the traditional embroidery worn by the Jordanian women. In comparison, often people show the least possible body with broad necklines and tight sleeves on purposes of modesty. If people want to maintain their values, they must adhere to them. However, people need to keep in mind that the manner they wear themselves reflect their culture. In comparison, citizens wearing their native clothes symbolize peace. That's how women in Jordan wear their traditional clothes carved with traditional embroidery to portray their

traditional culture non-verbally. Jordanian traditional clothing always played yet still serves a significant symbolic crucial role in the maintenance of national traditions and cultural heritage and even in the development of a sense of solidarity of the people. Jordanians put much more importance on individual care and fashion than people prefer to in the West. That's why the embroidery and traditional clothes are needed to be preserved to portray the non-verbal language of the cultural heritage of Jordan. The protection of the cultural heritage of every position demands a stable future that demands a reciprocal observance all nations beyond physical boundaries to enable the continuation including its shared heritage.

Embroidery

Jordanian folk embroidery is considered a fine art and one of the most important historical art in Jordan. Through designs and symbols, the Jordanian man was able to record his history and express the beliefs and patterns of social thinking from the customs and traditions that Jordanians have inherited over the centuries (Al-Aghbry, 2019)

That various geometric drawing that the woman draws with her needle on the cloth of her dress, or on any other piece of cloth she wants, makes it a heritage scene, like a beautiful engineering painting that dazzles the viewers.

The art of embroidery that women practiced in the past continues, as women continue to spread their creativity by making it a handcraft profession that distinguishes her.

The art of embroidery is considered one of the ancient folk arts of dazzling beauty and masterfully depending on the needle and thread and high artistic flair to draw artistic paintings with bright and beautiful threads embroidered on clothes and fabrics as aesthetic paintings in multiple forms, carrying with them the legacy of the past and its originality (Al-Shunnaq, 2018).

Embroidery has gotten one of the biggest and quickest developing financial divisions around the world. Nations like Jordan have created arrangements to renew this part, since they completely perceive as compelling apparatus on formation of business, financial development, and destitution easing just as commitment on the Gross Domestic product (GDP) (UNCTAD, 2013). Embroidery is one of the most significant segments in Jordan's economy. Jordan has gotten one of the most noticeable handcraft objections in the Middle East, particularly for unfamiliar sightseers. Moreover, Handicraft is one of the key drivers for the GDP for Jordan (Alshatnawi, 2013).

Embroidery are unique and impalpable items that speak to the cultural heritage and conventions of any nation, area or neighborhood system (Brandis & Jordan-Fahrbach, 1997). Without a doubt embroidery have become an imperative piece of cultural the handicraft industry. Undoubtedly, whatever the kind of the handicraft industry, the vacationer frequently takes home the compulsory keepsake. The United Nation World The handicraft industry Organization (UNWTO) expressed in the specialized note that " vacationers consistently buy as a reminder for those not going with or as tokens of the nations or spots, they visited". In this way, for vacationers, embroidery is an image for their visit, the spots they have visited and the encounters they had.

Notwithstanding their socio-cultural significance, thorough work can majorly affect financial improvement through work creation, unfamiliar trade income and supported financial development. They can likewise help moderate the rustic to metropolitan movement just as decrease the neediness (June, 2004). Moreover, there is

additionally a developing acknowledgment that the security and safeguarding of embroidery is a significant component of supportable improvement strategies.

Numerous nations have built up a few systems and arrangements to protect, create and showcasing this piece of heritage. Also, global associations, for example, Joined Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Association (UNESCO) and International Trade Center (ITC) have dispatched different gatherings and workshops in request to improve and build up the thorough work area. Unique need is provided to advertising so as to showcase this division on the worldwide exchange. These applied endeavors demonstrate the extraordinary potential for the embroidery to improve and build up the economy division. This infers that, whenever oversaw and grew suitably, embroidery can bring about exceptional yields. Moreover, thorough work requires basic procedures, nearby crude materials furthermore, low capital speculation, just as the capacity to work at home. Subsequently, low boundaries to passage empower individuals to enter this area with negligible capital (Mustafa, 2011).

In Jordan, careful work including an assortment of artworks that are discovered everywhere on over the nation, for example, customary material, stoneware, glass, wood, sand jugs, mosaic, etc. Jordan customary thorough work are an indispensable aspect of the nation's cultural heritage and customs. Moreover, embroidery division is a basic piece of the handicraft industry. In the same way as other different nations around the globe, Jordanian embroidery face various difficulties, affecting the turn of events and improvement of this area. These difficulties run from the executives and authoritative issues and guidelines to financial issues just as advertising and mindfulness.

The Current Status of Handicrafts in Jordan is lucky that is wealthy in cultural heritage assets that are discovered everywhere on over the nation, for example, archeological and conventional locales, exhibition halls and embroidery. Characteristic heritage is another significant piece of Jordan heritage. With respect to the embroidery, Jordan has numerous lovely and intriguing embroidery that mirror the nation's cultural heritage and conventions. In understanding to the Jordanian Guideline, the Jordanian embroidery incorporate conventional dress of women.

Previously, embroidery had an incredible significance as a homegrown necessity, and have been related with the style what's more, method of individuals' living. Notwithstanding, because of the cultural and financial changes in Jordan, these embroideries experienced disregard for quite a while and some of them are compromised with annihilation, which significantly affected its decrease (Maffi, 2009). In the light of the abovementioned, it is evident that there is decent variety in the creation of thorough work in Jordan. Tragically, there is no factual data about the embroidery area, just hardly any special cases are to be seen. Other than the cultural and cultural significance of the thorough work in Jordan, the thorough work part likewise assumes a significant job in the financial advancement as a component of the handicraft industry. The financial significance of the part likewise lies in its work potential and low capital venture (Mustafa, 2011).

There is no official body that is answerable for sorting out and creating thorough work part in Jordan. The Service of Industry and Trade, Ministry of Handicraft and Relics, Ministry of Cultural Development and Ministry of Culture, these services and other worldwide subsidizing organizations, for example, the European Union (EU) and the Joined State Agency for International Development (USAID) have applied endeavors in subsidizing and supporting the embroidery division in Jordan. In any case, a large portion of these endeavors to create and compose the segment flop because of the need of an incorporated arranging and coordination between them. This has thus left the area on edge and without vision (Banihani, 2020).

In agreement to the Handicraft Law 20/1988, the Ministry of Handicraft and Antiquities has a huge task to carry out in overseeing, creating and showcasing the thorough work in Jordan. Notwithstanding the above services, there are two principal affiliations speak to the embroidery area in Jordan with regard to controlling and regulating the division. The first is The Jordan Handicrafts Traders Association (JHTP) which is enrolled under the Ministry of Handicraft and Antiquities, furthermore, is the official body for permitting thorough work makers furthermore, merchants in participation with the Ministry of Handicraft and Artifacts. The Jordan Handicrafts Producers Affiliation (JHP) which is enrolled under the Ministry of Culture, and incorporates entrepreneurs and representatives of formal workmanship workshops. In any case, these two affiliations don't address the issues of the division in terms of creation and promoting.

Other than the legislative associations, the NGO's moreover have assumed a significant part in creating and supporting thorough work division in Jordan. The significant players of NGO's in embroidery advancement in Jordan are the Royal Society for the Conservation of Nature (RSCN), Noor Al Hussein Establishment (NHF), Jordan River Foundation (JRF) and The Jordanian Hashemite Fund for Human Development (JOHUD). In any case, these NGO's are confronted with a few issues, for example, disorderly advertising and lacking business sector data, their missions are covered and they viewing for a similar reserve and copying endeavors (Banihani, 2020).

Samples of Embroidery in Jordan

Women in northern Jordan excelled in embroidery, for the abundance of threads and the ease of obtaining them, whether from Syria or northern Palestine, made them embroider the bottom of their dress with hollow designs embroidered in white or blue that show the aesthetics of the design and decorate the dress or add a white piece of cloth dyed with indigo so that it becomes tilted to blue and then embroidered on it. The Jordanian woman in the north used a special stitch for embroidery, from which many beautiful patterns were embroidered. Then these designs evolved by introducing new colors and diversifying the design.

As for women in the Jordan Valley, the garment is distinguished by long lines of embroidery that are used to sew cloth together in an artistic way. The dress of Al-Adwaniyah (from the Adwan clan living in the Jordan Valley) was distinguished by the colors that came in the form of colorful lines sometimes decorated with small colored flowers.

As for the Maani woman, she was not interested in embroidery, due to her distance from the cities and her dependence on the itinerant merchant, she excelled in diversifying the fabric and its colors by sewing these colors together in an artistic way. But she excelled in her home furnishings, such as mattresses and pillows, and she used an artistic and primitive method of stretching and fixing threads, which gave primitive, spontaneous and beautiful artistic models that distinguished her from other regions of Jordan. Inventing history and heritage throughout the Jordan valley and the cultural heritage and message non-verbally displayed by the traditional embroidery carved on the dresses

One case of the dialogic connection among public and neighborhood portrayals of ancestral culture is to be found in the changing implications of the dilug, the conventional embroidered dress, for the clans of the Jordan Valley. The dilug is a dark, full-length, long-sleeved, embroidered dress, worn by moderately aged and more established ladies as a feature of their everyday clothing. The machine-embroidered flower or mathematical examples, done in either the glossy silk fasten (Tarrah) or chain line (Tab'a), differ and no single example is related to a specific clan (Beidelman, 1989). "A regular dilug is embroidered with around four to six spools of embroidery string around the edges of the sleeves, neck area, and stitch. Fancier dresses use up to 25 spools of string and cost about JD 45 or US \$1 35 of every 1981. On these more detailed dresses numerous groups of embroidery run the length of the dress notwithstanding a lavishly embroidered burden and groups around the stitch, shoulders and sleeves.

In spite of the fact that customarily made of cotton, ladies currently like to utilize manufactured textures in light of the fact that artificial materials last more and require less upkeep. Dilug are approximately cut, sufficiently adequate to wear all through a pregnancy, and the slipover is low enough in the front for ladies to nurture their babies. A long-sleeved dress and jeans are generally worn underneath so that the dilug can be lifted up and took care of around the midsection to shield it from getting filthy or underneath while working. Dilug are worn with an assortment of head scarves-strong white, the red or dark checked kafiyah, or on the other hand most ordinarily, a red or dark scarf with a brilliant paisley outskirt. Moderately aged and more seasoned ladies typically plait their hair and wear their scarves tied around the head of the head with them interlaces hanging unrestricted from underneath the scarf. More youthful ladies as a rule wear Western attire. School-matured young ladies wear the required long-sleeved, knee-length uniform dresses to class and wear comparative dresses or skirts and shirts somewhere else (Aitcheson et al. (2017). About a large portion of the young ladies wore a head spread during the time of my exploration from 1981-1982 and 1984. The individuals who did normally did as such as a statement of their humility thus wore plain strong shaded scarves, which they tied in an assortment of ways, the entirety of which totally secured their hair. Extravagant dilug are regularly chosen by young ladies to wear to authentic capacities. For instance, during the 1984 parliamentary by-races, 'Abadi young ladies filled in as the nearby agents of up-and-comers in the ladies' surveying stations. These young ladies, who regularly wore Western apparel, wore dilug for the event. Dilug were additionally worn by the senior class from the Deir 'Alla Optional School for Girls for their secondary school graduation. What's more, dilug are habitually picked by young ladies for their clothing at weddings, or when getting down to business to shop/be saw by possible spouses, or presenting before the anthropologist's camera (Zeidan & Lughod, 1989).

The dilug has consistently been dependent upon development just as changing business sector and political powers. Up until the 1930s dresses were made of handwoven cotton, cloth or silk and embroidery string was home-colored with vegetable and bug colors (Kawar & Nasir, 1980). Around 1930 machine-delivered textures opened up in the business sectors and mercerized cotton strings supplanted silk embroidery strings. The essential maker of this sort of embroidery string, Dollfus-Mieg and Cie. (DMC), likewise delivered design books that by the 1930s were "flowing among town ladies, presenting a path of new European examples and plans" (Kawar & Nasir, 1980). 'Abadi ladies recount changing dress styles. They state they used to wear the long what's more, plentiful thobs still connected with the town of Salt, which they collapsed over a belt (shuwayhiyyeh). Likewise, they portray textures, for example, malas and embellishments, for example, the red and dark silk Aleppo head scarves that are not, at this point an aspect of their closet.

Lately dilug, alongside other "customary" ensembles, have gotten expanding public consideration in Jordan and globally. A lot of banners and a schedule with photos of ladies wearing fine instances of perfectly embroidered customary outfits were created. Alia, the Jordanian aircraft, has supported various design shows of ladies demonstrating conventional dresses. One of the most widely recognized sorts of projects circulated on Jordanian TV is that of folkloric moving acted in bright folkloric outfits (Saunders & Gilmore, 1988). In 1987 the broad private assortment of Widad Kawar of Palestinian and Jordanian outfits was displayed in Cologne under the joint support of Queen Noor and Baroness von Weizsacker. The display was joined by a detailed inventory, with parts composed by anthropologists and antiquarians of Jordan examining the history and ethnographic settings of these outfits. (This display is currently appearing at the Institut du Monde Arabe in Paris.)

The Jerash Festival, a yearly cultural celebration set in the Roman remnants of Jerash, incorporates among its numerous worldwide and neighborhood cultural exercises gatherings of youthful Jordanians who wear "customary" ensembles and perform "folkloric" moves. Sovereign Noor introduced the first Jerash celebration in 1981 wearing a wonderfully embroidered outfit, one which didn't speak to any single clan or town yet which was a perfectly fine case of the consolidated conventions of the zone. Both the King and Queen wear a wide assortment of attire military outfits when visiting the different military units and institutes, tailored suits while accepting Western appointments, a top and outfit while managing a college graduation, etc. The appropriation of these different clothes not just conveys the message that the King and Queen are of the individuals, yet in addition adds authenticity to the establishments and practices being referred to, for this situation the wearing of customary embroidered dresses (Five Year Plan for Economic and Social Development, 1987).

In the Jordan Valley the preoccupation of dilug from their ordinary settings, that is, as the attire of moderately aged ladies, and the setting of them in new settings, for example, a secondary school graduation or a public political decision, accuses these dresses of emblematic worth. Working together with the public valorization of ancestral culture, the checked wearing of dilug by young ladies has become an image of ancestral character and, by augmentation, of Jordanian personality. For the ladies of the 'Abbad, the wearing of an all-around embroidered dress, similar to a bit of gold gems, is a public demonstration of status. But since the dilug have become images of the Bedouin's ancestral heritage, the wearing of a dilug by more youthful ladies has an extra certain ethical valuation. A young lady who wears a dilug is alluded to as muhtaramah. Muhtaramah implies regarded, loved, and regarded. The outfits worn by unmarried ladies, albeit commonly cut to be snugger than the dresses worn by wedded ladies, are looser than generally Western attire (Al-kheder et al. 2009).

The dilug's decency isn't just because of the way that the dresses are generally baggy and an unassuming decision of clothing. Indeed, young ladies with fundamentalist proclivities want to wear a plain, cover like dress which they feel agrees with the Koranic order that a lady ought not to cause to notice herself. Conversely, dilug are gaudy and gay, embellished with groups of blossoms and overflowing with shading. Since dilug represent "Bedouinness" and, by expansion, "Jordanians," their determination for wear by young ladies is a political proclamation what's more, one that meets with public gestures and remarks of endorsement by the nearby network. The certainty that I wore a dilug was a rehashed wellspring of remarks of this sort and some 'Abbadis announced with endorsement that my wearing a dilug had expanded the ubiquity of these dresses among nearby ladies. To the degree this was the situation, it mirrors the impact of their consciousness of Westerner's and the public first class' energy about these "people" parts of their way of life (Fakhouri & Haddad (2017).

Wearing such dresses is esteemed a noteworthy activity and, as other respectable acts, the honor it gives holds fast not exclusively to the lady wearing it however to her family and to her clan at huge." For my situation, the way that I indicated regard for this good component of their way of life expanded my own decency, which thus considered regard the 'Abbadis for facilitating me. This mirror-like duplication of honor is additionally clear in the following case of the dialogics of ancestral self-portrayals.

Substantial and elusive cultural heritage together express the lavishness and assorted variety of the world's cultural customs. In the handicraft industry, visiting distinctive cultural locales is considered as the principal heritage fascination, while immaterial cultural heritage frequently is seen as optional to the involvement with such locales. Numerous handcrafters would stop at a store or on the other hand workshop selling conventional workmanship things. An indispensable piece of handcrafters' experience is "Embroidery's", they speak to nearby conventions and indigenous populaces, they likewise represent the places visited by sightseers, the encounters they had, and a gift to be taken for companions and family members (Kawar & Nasir, 1980). Other than inspiring magnificent recollections by sightseers when taking a decent quality workmanship home, it excites the enthusiasm of other people who see it to visit the objective. Handmade items as unmistakable parts furthermore, craftsmanship as being elusive in culture are among the assets activated in the handicraft industry. Abusing these assets for the handicraft industry designs is of an incredible importance to practical turn of events. Such importance comes from the way that assembling customary creative items produces both salary and work openings.

In addition, such items are one of the methods through which a network presents its qualities and spiritualities; what's more, not less significant, they structure a fundamental part from the cultural and cultural personality sent through ages (Robinson and Picard 2006). Such advantages of embroidery are to be found in nations relying upon the handicraft industry as an essential financial segment. For Jordan, the handicraft industry is framing 14% of absolute GDP, it is the Kingdom's biggest fare division, second biggest private division boss, and second most elevated maker of unfamiliar trade.

Folk costume for women

The dress of the Bedouin woman consists of a veil (the mulfa) of black and white cloth or headscarves, which is wrapped over the head, and then wears over the mulfa (al-habriya), meaning the headband that blinds the head and is made of colored silk, as a headwear. As for the body dress, it consists of a long black dress called (Malas) or (Abu Ruisha), over which a garment (Al-Madraqah) is worn, which is decorated and colored, called (Saya), which is embroidered with (welt) threads of blue color and is usually embroidered by hand or plain black and from the forms of dresses (Madareq).

Abu Rudeine: It is without sleeves, and a full sleeve shirt is worn underneath.

Abaabi garment: It has three folds and resembles the salty garment (16 cubits), and over it the broadcloth dammer is worn, so the woman wears it over the saiyat, also called (the Muqatana), and it is made by hand.

Among the distinctive women's fashion is a belt called (Al-Shuwaihi), which is woven from embellished silk, with fringes hanging down to the knee, and this belt has almost disappeared. The Bedouin jewelry consists of gold and silver represented by (the Turki) on the head, the earring, and the (Wardina) that is placed on one side of the nose from below, and the (Arran) that is attached in the middle of the nose from the inside hanging down until it covers the middle of the upper and lower lip of the mouth, and the (Kurdan) around

the neck and finally (the Hijoul), which are the anklets in the legs, the (Arran) and the (Hijool) have almost disappeared.

<http://www.sha3erjordan.net/lovedesert/news.php?action=view&id=2383>

Significance of the Study

There are many aspects of heritage and its parts, which constitute the existential dimension of any society, and heritage represents the privacy of all societies, no matter how close they are to each other, and no matter how similar we find, but when we look closely at the heritage, we will find that this privacy represents the existentialism and identity of each community separately.

Among these communities is Jordan, which is a country rich in its different heritage, whether it is food, clothing, folklore, singing, dancing, songs and music, customs and traditions, and even the dialect, and all of us are interested in the vocabulary of this heritage and praise it, and in Jordan the media is interested in it through TV shows, songs and other things, from here, the researcher tried to monitor examples of traditional Jordanian dress for some geographical areas in the north, center and south of the Kingdom of Jordan, in addition to the Bedouin traditional dress.

MEHODOLOGY

The researcher followed the descriptive analytical approach, she talked about the costume of each region in Jordan, and included pictures of the traditional cloth of some cities in Jordan, along with a discussion about each. The researcher chose Ajloun to symbolize the north of Jordan, Al-Salt to symbolize the middle, and Maan to symbolize the south of Jordan. The costume of each area sends a special message about the environment, types of

THE ANALYTICAL STUDY

Embroidery Techniques and Styling

The embroidery string comprised of normally colored silk. Yet, since the 1930s, strings imported from Europe have been usually utilized. For the shading, overwhelmingly natural blends, protected by Fermentation were utilized. The most significant color was indigo (*indigofera Argentina*) with which one could color the texture in various shades of blue. The hazier the subsequent shading was, the more noteworthy the exertion that must be made and the more valuable turned into the last material. To color textures a hazier shade, the way toward plunging the texture must be rehashed again and again.

Carmine was utilized to make a seriously splendid red. This color was gotten from the cochineal creepy crawly which breeds on desert flora. Red was likewise gotten from madder, a base of the local regular madder plant (*rub tinctorum*). Whenever blended indigo and basic madder deliver purple and orange tones. Yellow was delivered with saffron (*crocus sativus*). Any shading could be made hazier by including pomegranate skin (Cheah, 2008).

The embroidery styles: Cross-fasten was the most well-known strategy utilized wherever in Jordan. Cross-join is additionally called fallacy, in light of the fact that this sort of embroidery was fundamentally done by worker ladies who are called fellaheen in Arabic. In Jordan the encompassing territories, framing embroidery was especially well known. With this method, cording of silk or silver string dunked in gold water was sewed to the texture.

The dresses in focal and southern Jordan were twofold length with the abundance texture hung over the belt to frame a pocket; they had long, typically pointed sleeves. The materials were not woven in Jordan yet imported from Palestine or Syria. The embroidery plans on dresses in Kerak show the impact of Palestinian embroidery. It is said this was because of Palestinian outsiders who got comfortable Kerak even before the First World War. Around then, there were not fringes in the area, and movement to and fro between what is currently Palestine and Jordan was normal. Movement was particularly solid between Karak (Medeghini et al., 2013).

Salt dress: The Salt dress is particular for its size; particularly the length of the dress' skirt and sleeves. The ladies wear it in what is known as a twofold wrap; that is, a lady belts the dress, so one layer hangs down over another, occasionally nearly to her feet. This makes a valuable pocket at the wearer's midsection. The dress requires sixteen meters of dubeit texture. Blue groups of indigo-colored texture run vertically on the sides and sleeves, and furthermore around the fix. These groups both reinforce and improve the magnificence of the dress. Salt has consistently been a conspicuous market community, and has drawn Bedouins and locals from the encompassing zone. One can see the impact of the Salt dress in the outfits of different districts in Jordan (however, for a diminished scope). (Rasyidah, 2018).

Madraga, shosh, thaob or khalaga, rely upon the zone, is the conventional lady's dress in Jordan. It is dark with embroidery down the front that is splendid and mind boggling. Normally made by ladies, it is finished with embroidery plans went down through ages. Notwithstanding the little geographic territory of Jordan, the embroidery styles differ between districts. It is influenced by the earth, societal position and way of life, as rural, Bedouin and metropolitan networks. Leslie). (Sotomayor & García, 2019) uncovered that Middle East (counting

Jordan) was creating profoundly created embroidery as ahead of schedule as the fifteenth century B.C. Embroidery presently is an imaginative articulation of Jordanian personality (Library of Congress, 2020).

Fig.1: *Thaob* from Ramtha City, North of Jordan

Source: - <https://encyclocraftsapr.com/embroidery-jordan/>

Thaob is produced using silk and great texture items. Dark is primarily the shade of outfit textures utilized for embroidery works. Embroidery strings are made of fleece, cotton and silk. At times different materials, for example, dainty metal strips, valuable and semi-valuable stones, and sequins are utilized. Embroiderers in the past utilized neighborhood crude materials, for example, plants or minerals to color the strings. Yet, presently they are utilizing the imported and hued yarns (T. E. of C. in W.-A. P. Region, 2020).

Each geographic territory has various components and improving plans got from nearby condition. By and large, designs contain flower, plants, mathematical themes and flying creatures (Library of Congress, 2020).

Embroidery items are broadly utilized as blessings. Customary weaved thaob are made to be worn by ladies, particularly during social occasions, festivities and public celebrations. In Jordan embroidery items are additionally inserted into furniture and frill, including placemats, pads, pendants, packs, cloaks and handbags. Previously, it involved honor for a lady of the hour to make her own embroidery before moving to conjugal home.

The assessed number of ladies who are associated with embroidery across Jordan is more than 5,000. Embroidery items are accessible in various crafted works stores, for example, guest focuses and in numerous city intersections just as showrooms of inns; it additionally accessible on the web. As of late, style shows were performed to display the Jordan customary dresses (Library of Congress, 2020).

The Bedouin Costume

A Bedouin woman

The dress of the Bedouin woman consists of several parts, each part of which has a name of its own and also has its own embroidery. After the woman has finished embroidering these parts, she gathers them and connects them to each other, forming the beautiful Arab dress that we know and familiarize with, and the parts of the dress are:

The Collar (Qabba), the front body (Badan Quddami), the back body (Badan Warrani), the (Banayeq), and the sleeves.

The Qabba: It is the upper part of the dress from the side of the chest, and it is a square piece with dense embroidery that covers the entire chest, and on the top there is the neck opening, which is a circular opening called the collar, from which emerges from the front a rectangular opening facing downward called the pocket opening, and under the Qabba there is a lining from the fabric of the dress itself. The Qabba is the one that reveals the beauty and the splendor of the garment, and it should be noted that the regular Qabba is the one that is sewn to the front body, while the dome that is sewn on a single piece of cloth is called a “nomadic Qabba,” and then it is installed on the body afterward.

The front body (Badan Quddami): It is the front part of the garment fabric and starts from the bottom of the garment to the top of the shoulders, and is embroidered on it with a wide vein at its right end starting from the bottom to the waist, and another similar vein on its left end and these veins are similar to the twigs on the back body and with the twigs. The twigs on the (banayeq) because they combine them when connecting the parts of the garment so that on the left side of the garment there is a twig from the front body, next to it the twig of the dress and after it, the back body, as well as on the right side of the garment. As for the embroidery on the empty part of the front body, its position varies according to the age of the woman, for the young girl, the embroidery increases on the body until it covers the largest part of it, while the elderly woman embroiders it on a thin ribbon from the bottom and leave the rest without embroidery.

The back body (Badan Warrani): is the part that meets the front body from the back, and the embroidery on it is similar to the embroidery on the front body.

<https://sites.google.com/a/mb.tikshuvdarom.org.il/link/lbas>

The Women folk costume for Huwaitat tribe’s women in the South of Jordan

The dress code for the Bedouin woman in the south, and the Huwaitat tribe in particular, which includes the Abu Tayeh, al-Jazi, Al-Najadat, Al-Maraiya, Al-Zawaidah, and Al-Sa`id clans is considered a distinctive costume and represents the character of the Bedouin woman and its unique features, beauty may be the most important of them, In addition to the fact that this dress is simple and facilitates movement because Bedouin women carry out a lot of responsibilities and work inside and outside the tent (bait Elshaar), therefore, she needs this outfit that combines its beauty on the one hand and ease of wearing on the other hand.

Al-Mahoethel

The Bedouin woman in the south wears the so-called (Al- Mahoethel), which is a wide garment made of a long piece of black cloth and its original color, and this garment has short sleeves, from which a piece called (the rudun) hangs when wearing it, the woman returns this dress back to surround the neck, and to shorten this long dress from the front and to take the shape that a woman wants, she ties it by a silk belt when worn around the waist area. The wealthy women and the daughters of the leaders (Al-Shuoukh) may be the most who are able to buy silk cloth, while others who are unable to purchase this expensive cloth use (Al-habar cloth) which is called (almlas). The rich women also wear a piece that is usually placed over the dress called (AljibbaAldamer), especially in the winter season, to prevent the cold, and this piece is made of (suinting) and maybe in black, blue, or red.

<http://jordangifts.org/home.asp?mode=more&NewsID=117&catID=7&Lang=arb>

Embroidery shapes and colors The Bedouin embroider her dress in red, green, white, or all of these colors together; and forms are usually beautiful and simple on the ends, and some women make it plain without embroidery. When the garment is folded with a silk belt, it is shortened from the front, so the Bedouin woman wears another piece under the dress called (the shirt), and the shirt is long and its sleeves are also long and with more than the color of red, green and blue, and its material may be either spring wool or silk.

On the head, the Bedouin woman puts the headband (al-Hattah), which is a piece of cloth made of silk or wool and is either black or dark brown and has various inscriptions and shapes in different colors. The head is also wrapped in it. It has beads in the colors of blue, red, yellow and green. The sharpeners are placed on the headband from the side, and some Bedouin women use instead of Almagbari (needle) made of gold, which is placed in the same way. Bedouin women have a special chemistry in the philosophy of life and beauty.

Salty folk costume

Woman Costumein Al-Salt

The Salti woman's dress has high aesthetic features, and is significantly different from the rest of the traditional costumes known in Jordan and the Levant. The costume of Salti woman is distinguished by its luxurious raw materials, in addition to its rich color, which reflects the nature of the city of Al-Salt, rich in its forests and green plains, which bloom most days of the year in the colors of flowers and plants.

Simple yet difficult to make

The dress is unique in the difficulty of making and preparing it, so more than three women participate in the manufacture of one garment, and it is characterized by its many styles. Daily work in the field is simple and practical, but it is beautiful and elegant, and for weddings and evening parties, dresses are also embroidered in various forms, including coral earring, pole, cups, etc., and include special jewelry and an embroidered headdress.

The costume of the Salti woman has contributed to refining her personality throughout history, and has given her great self-confidence, and strengthened her value as a woman first, and as a woman in society, as a mother, and as a citizen who performs her duties to the fullest.

Sameh, K. (2015). Jordanian women's folk costumes .. a chromatic celebration of life, retrieved from <https://www.addustour.com/articles/86384>

"Al-Khalaqa" a wedding dress

The Salti "Khalaqa" is characterized by soft and delicate embroideries that resemble a coral earring in the fluctuation of its colors, as well as the beauty of the embroideries of the nest with its drawings and the delicacy of the shapes of its flowers and butterflies and the softness of its birds, and also the Salti "Khalaqa" is distinguished by a beautiful and majestic detail, including the characteristic features of the "Khalaqa" from the detail of the headband and the beauty and dignity of "Al Ardan", the elegance of the embroidery of the shirt, the splendor of the embroidery of the tongues, the distinction of the shape of the titles, the stability of the luster of the majestic, the capacity of the curtains, the flow of the embroideries on the sides, and the delicacy of the details of the lower edges. All of this makes the Salti "Khalaqa" qualified to be a very elegant and beautiful dress for a bride to wear for a party of her life, and this can be done after introducing minor modifications to the original design of the "Khalaqa" to become suitable for a modern bride without neglecting the main features of the Salti "Khalaqa" that give it distinction from other traditional dresses. The white bride dress can be tailored from a slouchy and waisted silk fabric on the body, and it is embroidered with the Salti "Khalaqa" embroidery of corrugated coral earring with silk threads of silver, diamond, and white gradient colors. So that the sleeves - from the wrist to the elbow - and the chest of the white dress were waisted by a Chiffon Organza or a white georgette, as well as decorated with nest embroideries, such as the shirt of the Salti "Khalaqa", which is

embroidered with soft and delicate white drawings of flowers, butterflies, and hoopoe birds, and over the chiffon, the chest of the dress is covered with a sagging white silky cloth, and the "Qabba" of the dress is like the "Qabba" of the Salti "Khalaqa", including the entire embellishment of the embroidery of the tongue that reaches to the knee, So that later the silver glory could be fixed on the "Qabba" which were usually introduced by the groom when they sign their marriage (Al-Majali, 2019)

Traditional folk dress in Ajloun governorate

A woman wearing a folk dress (Brima)

Brima

A loose-fitting black dress that is worn by married women. It is 22 cubits long before the detail of a fabric called (smooth, maroon, or ink) and this is the fabric that was circulating among people for a period of time, and it is worn by women in Ajlouniyah and neighboring areas, folded three times, you tie belt of wide cloth over the second fold, then throw on it the third fold so that the belt is not seen due to the expansion of this garment (Al-Shuraidah, 2017).

Women adorn earrings, bracelets and so on, and every part of a woman's body had a specific adornment. We have jewelry for the head and necklaces, as well as for the hands and feet. Women acquire many types of jewelry and adornment, and they find in their wooden box studded with seashell, many types of

jewelry, until they reached the teeth, where we find among women what was called the tuck, which is a dental Jewelry, where a piece of gold is placed on the woman's tooth to give her beauty when smiling (Bani Mortada & Al-Shuraida, 2019)

Traditional folk dress in Maan governorate The Hormozi dress

The Hormozi dress is one of the traditional costumes that the "Maani" woman seeks to preserve and attaches great importance to it to reflect her originality and creativity, the Hormozi dress is considered one of the clothes that were distinguished by the women (the Kasbah of Maan), which kept its distinguished position with the Maani bride for a long period of time and distinguished her from the rest of the costumes in the governorates of Jordan. The Maani Hormozi dress is worn by the rich and the poor alike, and it consists of several pieces: the garment, the Jalaya, the headband, the cap, the belt, and its fabric is characterized by its presence in many different colors, such as orange-red, brown or light blue. The pieces of the cloth with which the Hormozi garment is filled is 30 cm wide, and we see the wisdom of this garment through the intelligence of the Maani woman, for the garment was a covering of the body that does not shape, describe or heal, and the dress is sewn in a long, loose form and long sleeves, and these sleeves are called (Ardon), it becomes wider when it is closer to the hand with to 71 cm, and it gradually narrows as it adheres to the dress, and shows the suitability of the

Maani woman's sense and religious commitment through the dress, which gives her modesty, dignity, and respect, despite the manifestations of the modern fashion.

In the form of rectangles, the dress is sewn with the so-called "Banaq" in a coherent manner, and the chest area is sutured in a loose fashion and is called "Al-Ub" and its prominence comes as a result of placing the belt on the waist, and pulling the garment to the top, and as a result the formation of a second layer of the dress which increases the dress's beauty and more modesty.

The garment also consists of a transparent, rectangular piece of cloth that is used as a headcover, and it is often black, called "Alshad", and a multi-colored piece of cloth not exceeding 12 cm in width and one and a half meters in length and is used to reduce the length of the garment and this is called the "belt" (Al-Hussan, 2014).

The ways to preserve Jordanian embroidery and help in the development in the of embroidery

Building up one authority body answerable for embroidery's segment: This would have clear components that emphasis on managing, controlling, and advancement of the embroidery part. This body ought to bring together completely applied endeavors concerning this part; plan systems and programs for embroidery improvement, coordinate this division into the public economy and support the research exercises for the ebb and flow and future requirements for this division. This body ought to likewise be under the umbrella of legislative association reference, for example, the Ministry of Handicraft and Antiquities and in regulatory and money related autonomy, so as to accomplish its work proficiency required and commit to serve this part.

Providing administrative components: This is acknowledged by giving Law for Jordanian embroidery's, associated to the Ministry of Handicraft and Antiquities. The Law incorporates managing the embroidery's creation and furnishing it with lawful structure. It is likewise incorporating consolation of the craftsman's and assurance their privileges, just as the security of locally embroideries from imported items. It is additionally acknowledged by reexamining the current Regulation 36/2002, so that gives adaptability in the meaning of embroidery, just as gives motivating forces to the retailers, so as to urge them to uphold Jordanian embroidery (Piccirillo& Cimino (2003).

Promoting and showcasing of embroidery's: The advancement strategy assumes an essential part in the advertising of embroideries. This is acknowledged through special and advertising programs (Audio, visual and print) at public also, worldwide level, lasting presentations and well-known business sectors in every district or region that produce also, deal embroidery's items, and creating Web Site for the locally embroideries. The administration ought to likewise grow step by step plan, so as to decrease of the imported craftsmanship items, just as advance and market the locally embroideries. Also, the proprietors of the vacationer's shops ought to be resolved to show in any event 70% of the locally thorough work as per the Regulation 36/2002. This is a significant component on advancement and promoting of the locally thorough work. Additionally, they should mindful about suitable bundling and showing their products in a great way, just as putting "Made in Jordan" mark. Likewise, serious projects for craftsman's could be sorted out, for example, a public honor, so as to support them in advancement and imagination in embroidery, too as to cause to notice them and their significant part to play in conservation of cultural heritage. Likewise, it is important for a public day for thorough work (Singh, 2019).

Providing crude materials: this is figured it out through setting up public associations accountable for providing crude materials to the skilled workers and trading workmanship items.

Providing Funds: This is acknowledged through setting up a National Fund with the point of supporting furthermore, financing the locally thorough work. This can be regulated by the significant services. This store gives the skilled workers with the important money related administrations for the getting. The private segment ought to be associated with supporting, contributing, and improvement of embroidery. In expansion, coordination ought to be taken with banks and money related associations, so as to fund the locally embroidery with sensible conditions (Adeel & Schuster, 2008).

Providing studies and exploration on embroidery's: this can be acknowledged by building up a public community for studies and exploration in locally embroidery's, with the point of documentation, advancement, innovativeness, plans, and improvement. Likewise, electronic information base ought to be made and incorporate all the far-reaching data about the locally embroidery furthermore, nearby craftsmen. What's more, the specific logical research managing thorough work and its associations ought to be energized and upheld, just as, the fundamental of coordination and joint effort with the social associations and colleges with respect to the advancement of embroidery.

Building up the craftsman's capacities: preparing is the essential component which any arrangement for thorough work advancement relies upon; it is likewise a significant method for creating thorough work. This is acknowledged through furnishing the craftsmen with the important capabilities also, abilities, so as to get items with high worth and quality that meet the hand crafter's taste and market request. For this, it is essential to setting up a middle for preparing, training and inventiveness on thorough work, all together to quality and raises the craftsman's capabilities. In expansion, coordination with the pertinent bodies ought to be done, so as to adapt

to the cutting-edge innovations in materials, plans, data, devices, estimating, costs, charges issues, and others, which help in creating and increment creation.

Introducing and attention to thorough work: the different media has an essential task to carry out in presenting and attention to the social, social, and financial significance of the embroidery. In this way, it is important to build up a limited time and media methodology (Audio, visual what's more, print.) which centers on presenting locally thorough work at public and worldwide level. Too, programs for lasting and intermittent displays in all the Jordanian territories ought to be created, just as, investment in the territorial and global shows. It is could be a favorable position to utilize the archeological and heritage destinations to show the artworks items. Moreover, social and heritage issues about locally thorough work ought to be embedded into the school educational programs, just as make a Web Site to presenting Jordanian thorough work globally, this can likewise offer types of assistance for contract also, trade these items outside the nation (Timár-Balázs&Eascop, 2012).

Discussion

Popular costumes have social, religious, economic and geographical uses and connotations. Each region has its own decorations. Affordable families used gold and silver threads and other expensive threads, fabrics and materials for embroidery, while poor families used cotton and woolen threads to decorate and embroider their garments. The colors of the traditional dress also indicate the age of the woman, as the red band is worn by the young woman, the black band is worn by the elderly woman, and the young married woman wears a garment decorated in different colors from the dress of a single woman, each according to his region. As each occasion has its own garment and decorations, such as work dresses, joy and sadness, and wedding dresses have a special position and certain specifications, so you find the colored dresses decorated with golden threads and find the white dress and its brightly embroidered decorations an expression of love and loyalty.

Jordanian folk embroidery is considered fine art and one of the most important historical art in Jordan. Through design and symbols, the Jordanian man was able to record his history and express the beliefs and patterns of social thinking from the customs and traditions that Jordanians have inherited over the centuries. The Jordanian dress also called the Madraga, and the embroideries decorated with it express the Jordanian identity and the deep connection with the land, heritage, and history. The Jordanian person was inspired by his design from his beliefs, history, and the surrounding environment, such as its flowers, leaves, ears of wheat, the shapes of its birds, and the meandering of its mountains and valleys, and its plains and valleys.

Despite the relatively small area of Jordan, Jordanian fashion is characterized by its very great diversity, especially for women, due to the diversity of Jordan's geography, where each region has its own designs with some outfits and commonalities between some regions.

Jordanian folk costumes have social, religious, economic and geographical uses and connotations. Each region has its own decorations, and families used golden and silver threads and other threads, fabrics and expensive materials for embroidery. Whereas poor families used cotton and woolen threads to decorate and embroider their clothes, and the colors of the Jordanian traditional dress also indicate the age of the woman, so the red band is worn by the young woman and the black band is worn by the old woman. The young married woman also wears a garment decorated in different colors from the single woman's dress, each according to its region, and for each occasion there is a dress and its own decorations such as work dresses, joy and sadness. Wedding dresses have a special position and specific characteristics, so you find colored dresses decorated with golden threads, and the white dress and its brightly embroidered decorations are an expression of love and loyalty.

Conclusion

The traditional Jordanian embroidery portrays the cultural heritage that was followed by the people of Jordan from decades. There are several techniques and styles that are used in the Jordan and these techniques and embroidery displays the vast cultural heritage of the country. These embroidery does not need to speak because the carving non-verbally portrays the historical and traditional culture of the country. The preservation and conservation of the traditional Jordanian embroidery is essential to teach the upcoming generation about the cultural heritage. The embroidery is also important for the development of the country so that the embroidery of the country can influence and reach every part of the world. Thus, the concluding remarks that the traditional embroidery displays the culture, tradition and history of the Jordan non-verbally to the world and the conservation of the embroidery is important.

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